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Level of Awareness Regarding Learning Disabilities

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ABSTRACT

Background:- Learning disabilities in school age children are one of the common problems that need the special attention from family, neighbors, social circles and teachers. Teachers are the primary that directly interacts with the kids & find out the child who is having difficulty in learning process. Teachers play a vast role in early diagnosis of student learning issues.

Methods: - A Non-experimental Descriptive Research Design & Quantitative Research Approach was used to assess the Learning disabilities. A convenient sampling technique was used to collect the data from elementary school teachers. Data was collected using self structured knowledge questionnaire. The main study data collection was obtained from 500 primary school teachers from 39 selected schools at district Dholpur Rajasthan from 05-12-20 to 30-3-21. Ethical clearance was obtained from Desh Bhagat University Mandi Gobindgarh Punjab and District Education Officer Elementary Dholpur Rajasthan study was found ethically exempted.

Results: - The study result revealed that majority 80% from urban area and 79.39% from rural area had average level of awareness whereas 2.69% of elementary school teachers from urban area and 1.82% from rural area had poor level of awareness. There was no association found between levels of awareness with selected socio-demographic variables. ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: - 80% of elementary school teachers were having the average levels of awareness about learning disabilities, while comparing with rural & urban school teachers there was no difference found about the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities.. There was no association found between levels of awareness score with selected socio-demographic variables.

Keyword :- Learning Disabilities, Teachers, Elementary School

Introduction:- Learning disabilities in school age children are one of the common problems that need the special attention from family, neighbors, social circles and teachers.¹ Children with a learning disability have trouble performing specific types of skills or completing tasks while the specific nature of these brain-based disorders is still not well understood, considerable progress has been made in mapping some of the characteristic difficulties of LD to specific brain regions and structures.² Learning refers to the most complex cognitive function of the brain and there should not be surprise that many children (as many as 5-10% worldwide) have difficulty to get basic information such as reading, writing, and mathematics.³ In India, around 13-14% of all school children are suffering from learning disorders. Unfortunately, most schools fail to handle such children learning abilities process.⁴

Background of the Study

The most common types of learning disabilities involve problems with reading, writing, math, reasoning, listening, and speaking.⁵

A study was conducted on knowledge and attitude toward learning disabilities among primary school teachers in dammam, qatif and alkhobar cities, K.S.A the study results revealed that two-thirds (75.4%) of participant's teachers had low Knowledge about learning disabilities. 51.8% respondents had a low attitude about learning disabilities. As well as, 65.6% of participant's teachers had low Knowledge and attitude about learning disabilities hence conclusion of the study was Primary school teachers who participated in the present study had poor Knowledge and attitude about learning disabilities.⁶

A study was conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude of primary school teachers regarding learning disabilities among children in selected schools of district Pulwama Kashmir. The study result revealed that majority of teachers 73.3% had moderate knowledge, 20.0% had inadequate knowledge whereas only 6.7% teachers had adequate knowledge on the subject. On attitude of primary school teachers, 93.3% teachers had most favorable attitude towards children with learning Disability. Only 6.7% teacher's showed favorable attitude. There was significant correlation between knowledge of teachers regarding learning disability and their attitude towards such children. There was significant association between marital status, Age of teachers with their attitude.⁷

A Descriptive study was conducted on level of Awareness on Learning Disabilities The study results reveals that elementary school teachers have an average level of Awareness on Learning Disabilities and there exist significant difference in the mean scores of Awareness on Learning Disabilities with respect to gender, locale, type of management but no significant difference exist in the mean scores of Awareness on Learning Disabilities with respect to teaching experience.⁸ similarly 35.5% of respondents had average knowledge, 29.1% had below average level of knowledge, 27.3% had good knowledge and very few of them had 8.2% excellent knowledge. There was also find a highly significant association between level of knowledge and socio-demographic variables with age, qualification, teaching experience, marital status, areas of residence, religion and source of information.⁹ The study results shows that 52.67 % have moderate knowledge and 47.33% primary school teachers have inadequate knowledge regarding learning

disabilities.¹⁰ Majority of teachers (64%) had average knowledge regarding specific learning disability.¹¹

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers.
2. To compare the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among rural and urban elementary school teachers.
3. To find out the association between level of awareness score with selected socio-demographic variables.

Hypothesis

H0- There is no significant relationship between level of awareness of learning disabilities among elementary school teachers with selected demographic variable

H1- There is a significant relationship between level of awareness of learning disabilities among elementary school teachers with selected demographic variable.

Methodology

Research Design: - A Non experimental descriptive research design was used in the present study & qualitative research approach was used.

Setting:-Selected schools of Dist Dholpur Rajasthan.

Population:-Elementary school teachers

Sample Size:-500 Elementary school teachers

Sampling Technique:-Non Probability Convenient Sampling

Sampling Criteria

Inclusion criteria

The elementary school teachers who:

1. Are working in selected elementary schools of Dist. Dholpur.
2. Are present during the period of data collection.
3. Are willing to participate in the study.
4. Able to read and write Hindi or English.

Exclusion criteria

1. Not willing to participate in the study
2. Not working in selected elementary schools of Dist. Dholpur.
3. Not available at the time of data collection

Description of tool

Tool consist of Two section

Section A The demographic information consist of following questions of Respondents i.e. age, gender, School Location , marital status , Religion , Type of School , Class being taught , Education Qualification,

Years of Experience

Section B Level of Awareness questionnaire- The tool consisted of 25 questions. For each question wrong answer minimum score will be 0 (Zero) and for the correct answer maximum score will be 1(one)

Data Collection

A written permission was obtained from the District education officer (Elementary) Dist Dholpur Rajasthan & Chief Block Education Officer Bari District-Dholpur Rajasthan. Prior to the data collection, the investigators familiarized themselves with the participants and explained to them the purpose of the study and assured them confidentiality of their response. An informed consent was obtained from the teachers and the tool was administered in the classroom setting at a comfortable time.

Results

Table 1 finding depicts that In the present study demographic variables finding is according to Age group majority of teachers 49.40% of elementary school teachers were in the age group of 21-30 years & 22.40% were in the age group of 41-50 years. According to the gender majority of teachers 57% of elementary school teachers were males and 43% of them were females. As per school location majority of teachers 67% were from urban area and only 33% from rural area. According to marital status Majority 57.80% of them were unmarried & 42.20% elementary school teachers were married. According to the religion of the teacher's majority 77.40% elementary school teachers was Hindu whereas only 2.60% of them were Christian. According to type of school Majority of teachers 60.80% of them were from private schools & 39.20% of elementary school teachers were from government schools. As per class being taught 59% of them were taught to upper primary school & 41% of elementary school teachers were taught to lower primary. Majority of teachers 44.80% were educated upto B.Ed whereas only 3.80% of them were having other qualification. Majority of elementary school teachers 51.40% were having working experience of upto 10 years whereas only 6.60% of them were having working experience of more than 20 years

Table 1: Frequency & Percentage distribution of elementary school teachers according to their demographic variables.

n=500

Demographic Variables	No. of teachers (f)	Percentage (%)
Age(yrs)		
21-30 yrs	247	49.4
31-40 yrs	141	28.2
41-50 yrs	112	22.4
Gender		
Male	285	57.0
Female	215	43.0
School Location		
Urban	335	67.0
Rural	165	33.0
Marital Status		
Married	211	42.2
Unmarried	289	57.8
Religion		
Hindu	387	77.4
Muslim	64	12.8
Christian	13	2.6
Other	36	7.2
Type of school		
Government	196	39.2
Private	304	60.8
Class being taught		
Lower Primary	205	41.0
Upper Primary	295	59.0
Educational Qualification		
Diploma/Certificate	176	35.2
B.Ed.	224	44.8
M.Ed.	81	16.2
Others	19	3.8
Years of experience		
≤10 yrs	257	51.4
11-20 yrs	210	42.0
>20 yrs	33	6.6

Objectives:-1 To assess the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers.

Table 2: Assessment with level of awareness score

n=500

Level of awareness score	Score Range	Level of Awareness Score	
		Urban Area	Rural Area
Poor	0-8	9(2.69%)	3(1.82%)
Average	9-17	268(80%)	131(79.39%)
Good	18.25	58(17.31%)	31(18.79%)
Minimum score		7	7
Maximum score		20	20
Mean awareness score		14.31±2.82	14.30±2.94
Mean % awareness Score		57.26±11.29	57.23±11.78

Table no-2 shows that 2.69% of elementary school teachers from urban area and 1.82% from rural area had poor level of awareness score, 80% from urban area and 79.39% from rural area had average and 17.31% from urban area and 18.79% from rural area had good level of awareness score.

Minimum awareness score for elementary school teachers of urban and rural area was 7 and maximum awareness score was 20.

Mean awareness score for elementary school teachers of urban area was 14.31 ± 2.82 and for rural area it was 14.30 ± 2.94

Objective 2:- To compare the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among rural and urban elementary school teachers.

Table 3: Comparison of level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among urban and rural elementary school teachers

n=500

Overall	n	Mean	SD	Mean Difference	t-value	p-value
Urban Area	335	14.31	2.82	0.007 ± 0.2	0.02	0.97
Rural Area	165	14.30	2.94			NS, $p > 0.05$

Table 3 revealed that while comparing the level of awareness regarding learning disabilities among urban and rural elementary school teachers. Mean, standard deviation and mean difference values are compared and unpaired 't' test is applied at 5% level of significance. The tabulated value for $n=500-2$ i.e. 498 degrees of freedom was 1.96. The calculated 't' value i.e. 0.02 are much less than the tabulated value at 5% level of significance for overall awareness score of learning disabilities which is statistically not acceptable level of significance. Hence it is statistically interpreted that the overall awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers was not significant. Thus the H_0 is accepted.

Objective 3:- To find out the association between level of awareness of learning disabilities with selected socio-demographic variables.

Table 4: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to age.

n=500

Age (yrs)	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	F-value	p-value
21-30 yrs	247	14.50 ± 2.99	2.12	0.12 NS, $p > 0.05$
31-40 yrs	141	14.35 ± 2.61		
41-50 yrs	112	13.83 ± 2.83		

Table no- 4 shows the association of awareness score with age in years of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 'F' values was 2.99 (df=2,497) which is much higher than the calculated 'F' i.e. 2.12 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.12 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that age in years of

elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 5 : Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to gender.

n=500

Gender	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	t-value	p-value
Male	285	14.48±2.81	1.56	0.11
Female	215	14.08±2.91		NS,p>0.05

Table No-5 shows the association of awareness score with gender of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 't' values was 1.96(df=498) which is much higher than the calculated 't' i.e. 1.56 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.11 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that gender of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score

Table 6 : Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to school location

n=500

School location	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	t-value	p-value
Urban	335	14.31±2.82	0.02	0.97
Rural	165	14.30±2.94		NS,p>0.05

Table No-6 shows the association of awareness score with school location of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 't' values was 1.96(df=498) which is much higher than the calculated 't' i.e. 0.02 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.97 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that school location of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 7: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to marital status

n=500

Marital Status	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	t-value	p-value
Married	211	14.32±2.86	0.08	0.93
Unmarried	289	14.30±2.86		NS,p>0.05

Table No-7 shows the association of awareness score with marital status of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 't' values was 1.96(df=498) which is much higher than the calculated 't' i.e. 0.08 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.93 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that marital status of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 8: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to religion

n=500

Religion	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	F-value	p-value
Hindu	387	14.26±2.91	0.28	0.83 NS,p>0.05
Muslim	64	14.50±2.8		
Christian	13	14.07±3.04		
Other	36	14.61±2.34		

This table No-8 shows the association of awareness score with religion of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 'F' values was 2.60(df=3,496) which is much higher than the calculated 'F' i.e. 0.28 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.83 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that religion of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 09: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to type of school

n=500

Type of school	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	t-value	p-value
Government	196	14.26±2.82	0.30	0.76 NS,p>0.05
Private	304	14.34±2.89		

Table No-09 shows the association of awareness score with type of school of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 't' values was 1.96(df=498) which is much higher than the calculated 't' i.e. 0.30 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.76 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that type of school of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 10: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to class being taught

n=500

Class being taught	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	t-value	p-value
Lower Primary	205	14.38±2.83	0.46	0.64 NS,p>0.05
Upper Primary	295	14.26±2.88		

Table No-10 results shows that the association of awareness scores with class being taught of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 't' values was 1.96(df=498) which is much higher than the calculated 't' i.e. 0.46 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.64 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that class being taught of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

Table 11: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to education

n=500

Education	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	F-value	p-value
Diploma/Certificate	176	14.48±2.89	1.44	0.22 NS,p>0.05
B.Ed.	224	14.41±2.87		
M.Ed.	81	13.82±2.90		
Others	19	13.63±2.00		

Table No-11 shows the association of awareness score with education of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 'F' values was 2.60(df=3,496) which is much higher than the calculated 'F' i.e. 1.44 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.22 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that educational level of elementary school teachers is statistically associated with their awareness score.

Table 12: Association of awareness score regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers in relation to years of experience

n=500

Years of experience	No. of elementary school teachers	Mean awareness score	F-value	p-value
≤10 yrs	257	14.11±2.64	1.93	0.14 NS,p>0.05
11-20 yrs	210	14.43±3.07		
>20 yrs	33	15.06±2.97		

Table No-12 shows the association of awareness score with years of experience of elementary school teachers regarding learning disabilities. The tabulated 'F' values was 2.99(df=2,497) which is much higher than the calculated 'F' i.e. 1.93 at 5% level of significance. Also the calculated 'p'=0.14 which was much higher than the acceptable level of significance i.e. 'p'=0.05. Hence it is interpreted that years of experience of elementary school teachers is statistically not associated with their awareness score.

DISCUSSION

It was concluded that 80% from urban area and 79.39% from rural area had average and 2.69% of elementary school teachers from urban area and 1.82% from rural area had poor level of awareness score The present study results were also supported by the Arifa S, Siraj SS ⁷ & also another study results were supported by the Seema Menon K.P ⁸ similarly & Charan Gopal Singh.⁹

Comparison of awareness regarding learning disabilities among urban and rural elementary school teachers. it is statistically interpreted that the overall awareness regarding learning disabilities among elementary school teachers was not significant. Findings were contradictory Seema Menon K.P.⁸

The Study finding reveled that there was no association found between level of awareness of learning disabilities with selected socio-demographic variables. Current study finding supported by Ghimire,

Conclusion

The present study finding shows that majority 80% of elementary school teacher were having average level of awareness whereas the lowest percentage 2.40% teachers were having poor level of awareness regarding learning disabilities. While finding the association of level of awareness with demographic variables no significant association found.

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Ethical clearance

It was obtained from, ethical committee of the Desh Bhagat University Mandi Gobindgarh Punjab & District Education Officer (Elementary) Dist-Dholpur, Chief Block Education office Bari Dist, Dholpur Rajasthan informed consent was taken from principals & respondents.

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Conflict of Interest: - All the authors do not have any possible conflicts of interest

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